

**MAKE UP TO STEP UP: ANALYZING THE EFFECTS OF PROJECT BASED
LEARNING APPROACH TO THE ENGLISH ORAL COMMUNICATION
SKILLS OF THE GRADE 11 STUDENTS IN MAGSAYSAY
NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL**

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14202198>

ABSTRACT

This study sought to analyze the effects of the Project-Based Learning (PBL) approach in developing the English oral communication skills of Senior High School (SHS) students. The researcher utilized the self-made rubric among Magsaysay National High School students in Mulanay District to conduct pretest and posttest. The intervention of the Step Program, using the PBL approach, took place after the pretest. The paired t-test was employed to compare the pre-test and post-test results. Additionally, Levene's variance equality test was utilized to measure the significance. Based on the investigation, the student's oral communication before implementing the PBL is 'developing with a range score of 10-15. Meanwhile, after the implementation, the student's scores improved (16-20) and were marked as 'proficient.' Furthermore, the test of significance on the effect of the Project-Based Learning approach on the Oral Communication Skills of the students indicated that the null hypothesis should be rejected if the p-value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05) and the Levene's test of equality of variance results on the different criteria that gauge the oral communication skills of the students: 'organization' with a significance level of .042, 'speaker knowledge,' 'audience adaptation,' 'language use' and 'delivery (non-verbal)' were all on the significance level of 0.000, results were less than the p-value, and this means that the PBL has significant effect to the enhancement of the student's oral communication skills. It can be noted that the PBL program can be utilized to enhance the learner's oral communication skills.

Keywords: *PBL, Step-Up, Oral Communications, Intervention*

INTRODUCTION

Oral communication serves various teaching purposes in general and within specific disciplines. Therefore, students are expected to communicate effectively. However, most hesitated to speak and utter words and use the target language, especially in rural areas like Magsaysay National High School in Mulanay District, making communication ineffective. Students are afraid to converse using the target language. They are not used to speaking the language, and often, they are hesitant to speak because they cannot pronounce the words or comprehend them. These instances challenge the teachers of Oral Communication. Furthermore, the students must meet the curriculum performance standard of the subject, which is to 'demonstrate effective use of communicative strategy in a variety of speech situations. Further, meet the learning competencies, 'exhibits appropriate verbal and nonverbal behavior in a given speech context' and 'engages in a communicative situation using acceptable, polite and meaningful communicative strategies.'

In line with the Sustainable Development Goal (SDG), education is at the heart of the 2030 agenda to ensure that lifelong learning opportunities for all, from early childhood to adult education and to ensure the effective learning and the acquisition of relevant knowledge, skills and competence. Hence, speaking effectively is a crucial goal of oral communication and provides students with skills they can use throughout their lives. Speaking is the primary means of communication used to express viewpoints, make arguments, offer explanations, convey information, and create impressions on others. On the other hand, students can communicate effectively in their personal lives, future workplaces, social interactions, and political activities by conducting meetings, presentations, discussions, arguments, and group work through project-based learning (PBL). PBL may be a teaching opportunity to practice speaking and will aid the teachers in oral communication to facilitate a practical speaking class. Moreover, students may position themselves to achieve a wide range of goals and become productive members of their communities once they muster the courage to speak communicatively. Furthermore, oral communication can be categorized into two parts, which students must be able to keep up with for them to go with the rapid changes in information technology and the various information resources; the first one is verbal communication, which is about written and spoken language. It also refers to our use of words. In contrast, non-verbal communication refers to communication that occurs through means other than words, such as body language, gestures, and silence, which makes English critical as the subject to study since this is the first worldwide language currently for communication and cultural reasons, further to collaborate with others. Hence, oral communication targets the students' communicative skills development to make them more functional individuals in the real world.

Meanwhile, Project-based Learning (PBL) is one of the approaches that focuses on teaching through the involvement of students in the investigation. Maulany (2013) found that implementing PBL in teaching English as a Foreign Language made students

actively engage in Project learning. Also, it enhanced the students' interest, motivation, engagement, and enjoyment. It encouraged social learning that could increase collaborative skills. In addition, Bas (2012) revealed that PBL improved the quality of learning and led to higher-level cognitive development through the students' engagement with complex and novel problems. Nonetheless, PBL can be a tool for improving the students' communicative competence. This can be used in the teaching and learning process, where the students create their learning at their own pace.

Hence, the researcher designed the STEP program using the Project-Based Learning (PBL) approach to examine its effects on developing students' English oral communication skills. Furthermore, this program may be used in the classroom to enhance students' creativity, critical thinking, and communicative competence.

The STEP Program is a Project-Based Learning (PBL) initiative at Magsaysay National High School to improve students' communicative competence through the Oral Communication subject. This learner-centred, integrative, collaborative program fosters holistic and meaningful learning experiences. It also encourages camaraderie among learners as they engage in the embedded activities. Additionally, PBL can be a tool to enhance classroom instruction, promoting not only communicative competence but also students' social skills.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the effects of the Project-Based Learning (PBL) approach in developing the English Oral Communication Skills of Senior High School (SHS) students in Magsaysay National High School, Mulanay, Quezon.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of Oral Communication Skills of the students before using the Project-Based Learning Approach?
2. What is the level of Oral Communication Skills of the students after using the Project-Based Learning Approach?
3. What is the mean gain in the Oral Communication Skills of the Students before and after using the Project-Based Learning Approach?
4. Is there a significant effect of the Project Based Learning approach on the English Oral Communication Skills of the students?
5. What Project-based Learning enhancement strategies can be produced after the investigation?

METHODOLOGY

This chapter elucidated the methodologies and protocols that enable the researcher to carry out the study effectively. This chapter focused on various aspects of

the research study, including the research design, research locale, research population and sampling, research instrument, data gathering procedure, and statistical treatment.

Research Design

This study utilized the descriptive method of research to gather information about the present conditions being examined. This method focused on current practices, situations, and prevailing conditions. Analyzing these conditions allowed the researcher to identify the necessary solutions for the study.

According to Best and Kahn (2014), descriptive research describes and interprets "what is." It is concerned with conditions or relationships, opinions, ongoing processes, evident effects, or emerging trends. While primarily focused on the present, it often considers past events and their influence on current conditions. Quantitative data analysis was applied to the responses of secondary students to determine the effects of Project-Based Learning (PBL) on their oral communication skills.

Research Locale

The study was conducted at DepEd Magsaysay National High School in Mulanay District I. The school offered a senior high school program, where the oral communication subject was part of the curriculum for the first semester. In here, the Magsaysay National High School students spoke various languages, and many were unfamiliar with a second language. In addition, Mulanay is a first-class municipality situated in the Third Congressional District of Quezon which is also called "Bondoc Peninsula". It has 28 barangays wherein 30,000 residents are living there. Mulanay is known for celebrating "Cocolunay" during its town fiesta.

In addition, Mulanayin earned their living through fisheries and agriculture. Also, Mulanay is 150 kilometers away from Lucena which can be accessed through riding buses and vans. Lastly, Mulanay has its neighboring towns namely; Catanauan, Buenavista, San Narciso and San Francisco.

Population and Sampling

The research participants were twenty-six (26) Grade 11 students currently enrolled in the oral communication subject. They were purposefully selected for the study.

Research Instrument

To determine the effects of the Project-Based Learning (PBL) Approach on students' oral communication skills, the researcher used a rubric when the pre-test and post-test were administered to assess the impact of the STEP program. The STEP program served as an intervention tool during the study and was implemented over four instructional sessions, each lasting 45 minutes. The students navigated the lessons and activities under the teacher's guidance. The sessions followed the planning, designing, and implementing phases, with assessments conducted to ensure student learning.

Pretest and Post Test Rubric in measuring the level of Oral Communication Skills of the Students

Name:	Date:	Score:
Grade 11: Section:	Teacher:	

Component	Emerging (0-12 points)	Developing (13-16 points)	Advanced (17-20 points)	Score
1. Organization	<p>The speech ideas are unfocused and the main purpose is unclear and difficult to identify. The introduction is undeveloped. Transitions may be needed. The presentation has no clear conclusion. The audience cannot understand the presentation because there is no sequence of information.</p>	<p>The main idea is evident, but the organizational structure may need strengthening. The introduction is not well designed. Transitions are available but not all are suited for each statement. There is supporting material but it is undeveloped. The conclusion is unstructured. The audience has difficulty understanding the presentation because the sequence of information is unclear.</p>	<p>Ideas are organized, developed, and supported to achieve a clear purpose. The introduction has an interesting hook to get the audience's attention. The main points are clear and organized effectively. The conclusion is satisfying and relates to the introduction. (If the purpose of the presentation is to persuade, a clear action step is identified and an overt call to action.)</p>	
2. Topic Knowledge	<p>The student does not grasp information and cannot answer questions about the subject. Few, if any, sources are cited.</p>	<p>The student has a partial grasp of the information. Supporting material is not</p>	<p>The student has a clear grasp of information. Citations are introduced and attributed</p>	

	<p>Citations are misattributed. Inaccurate, generalized, or inappropriate supporting material is presented but not all suited to the main ideas. Over-dependence on notes is observed.</p>	<p>strong and lacks originality. Citations are generally introduced and attributed appropriately. The student is at ease with expected answers to all questions but fails to elaborate. Over-dependence on notes is observed.</p>	<p>appropriately and accurately. Supporting material is original, logical, and relevant. The student demonstrates full knowledge (more than required) by answering all class questions with explanations and elaboration. Speaking outline or note cards are used for reference only.</p>	
<p>3. Audience Adaptation</p>	<p>The presenter is not able to keep the audience engaged. Lack of interest or confusion is evident from the audience's verbal or nonverbal feedback/expressions. Topic selection does not relate to audience needs and interests.</p>	<p>The presenter keeps the audience engaged most of the time. When feedback indicates a need for idea clarification, the speaker attempts to clarify or restate ideas. Generally, the speaker demonstrates audience awareness through nonverbal and verbal behaviors. Topic selection and examples are appropriate for the</p>	<p>The presenter effectively keeps the audience engaged. Material is modified or clarified as needed given the audience's verbal and nonverbal feedback. Nonverbal behaviors are used to keep the audience engaged. The delivery style is modified as needed. Topic selection and examples are interesting and relevant for the audience and occasion.</p>	

		audience, occasion, or setting. Some effort to make the material relevant to the audience's needs and interests.		
4. Language Use (Verbal Effectiveness)	Language choices are limited, unclear, or biased, peppered with slang or jargon, too complex, or too dull. Language is questionable or inappropriate for a particular audience, occasion, or setting.	The language used is mostly respectful or inoffensive. Language is appropriate, but word choices are not particularly vivid or precise.	Language is familiar to the audience, appropriate for the setting, and free of bias; the presenter uses "code-switch" (use a different language form) when needed and appropriate to the scenario. Language choices are vivid and precise.	
5. Delivery (Nonverbal Effectiveness)	The delivery detracts from the message; eye contact is very limited; the presenter tends to look at the floor, mumble, speak inaudibly, fidget, or read most of the speech; gestures and movements are jerky or excessive. The delivery appears inconsistent with the message. Nonfluencies ("ums") are used excessively. Articulation and pronunciation tend to be sloppy. The poise of composure is lost during any distractions.	The delivery generally seems effective – however, effective use of volume, eye contact, vocal control, etc. is not consistent; some hesitancy is observed. Vocal tone, facial expressions, clothing, and other nonverbal expressions do not detract	The delivery is extemporaneous -- natural, and confident, and enhances the message – posture, eye contact, smooth gestures, facial expressions, volume, pace, etc. indicate confidence, a commitment to the topic, and a willingness to communicate. The vocal tone, delivery style, and clothing are consistent with	

	Audience members have difficulty hearing the presentation.	significantly from the message. The delivery style, tone of voice, and clothing choices do not seem out-of-place or disrespectful to the audience or occasion. Some use of nonfluencies is observed. Generally, articulation and pronunciation are clear. Most audience members can hear the presentation.	the message. Delivery style and clothing choices suggest an awareness of expectations and norms. Limited use of nonfluencies is observed. The articulation and pronunciation are clear. All audience members can hear the presentation.	
TOTAL				

Data Gathering Procedures

The following steps were undertaken to collect data for the study: preparing the rubric for the pre-performance and post-performance tests, developing the STEP program, and obtaining permission from Dr. Rommel C. Bautista, Schools Division Superintendent; Dr. Rebie A. Marciano, PSDS of Mulanay District I; and Mrs. Aurea M. Osen, School Head of Magsaysay National High School will administer the performance tasks and the program.

Upon the validation of the rubric for the pre-performance and post-performance tasks and the STEP program, the researcher consulted Dr. Lydia F. Salumbides, Dr. Joyyeth C. Bautista, and Dr. Menching L. Samson for further validation. Finally, the assessment, analysis, and interpretation of the investigation's results were conducted.

The researcher sought assistance from the available language teachers to observe and rate the Grade 11 students as they delivered their impromptu speeches for their pre-performance task. After this, the researcher implemented the STEP program with the

Grade 11 students, and upon completion, the language teachers also conducted the post-performance task.

The administration of the performance tasks and the program's implementation began during the first semester when the Oral Communication subject was offered. The STEP program consisted of four sessions, each lasting 45 minutes, held once a week, specifically on catch-up Fridays. This scheduling allowed students to prepare for public presentations while minimizing disruptions to regular class discussions.

The Project-Based Learning component occurred over four instructional sessions within a month, each lasting 45 minutes. The lessons were divided into four sessions, with topics selected based on students' interests. Additionally, the students undertook an English Broadcast project as part of the STEP program, where they developed a news broadcast in English that focused on real-world issues, enhancing their speaking skills and language use. The discussion of Project-Based Learning took place over three sessions, and in the fourth session, the students presented their English broadcasts.

Further instructions were provided to clarify specific terms in the test before the study was completed.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The effect of the STEP program was measured by conducting both the pre-performance and post-performance tasks, with the post-performance task administered after the intervention of the STEP program.

Subsequently, the collected data was tallied, tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted. Descriptive statistics were used to assess the effect of the STEP program. Furthermore, a paired t-test was employed to compare the pre-test and post-test results. Additionally, Levene's test of equality of variance was utilized for data analysis.

RESULTS

Part 1: The Level of English Oral Communication Skills of the Students before using the Project-Based Learning Approach

Table 1. *Level of English Oral Communication Skills of the Students in terms of Organization*

Score Range	F	%	Overall Percentage Score	Mean Score	Verbal Interpretation
16-20	6	23.08	66.92	13.38	Developing
10-15	19	73.08			
0-5	1	3.85			

Legend: “Proficient (16-20)”, “Developing (10-15)”, “Emerging (0-5)”

Table 1 shows the level of English Oral Sommmunication Skills of the students in terms of organization before implementing the STEP program as a Project-Based Learning approach.

Based on the investigation, most students are at the “*developing*” level, developing mean that the students cannot fully create a good introduction and the transitions are not fully structure, with a frequency score of 19 (73.08%) and a mean score of 13.38, resulting in an overall percentage score of 66.92, which falls within the score range of 10–15. This indicates that the students are still developing their organizational skills in speaking, and their organizational structure needs strengthening. According to Tas (2022), students at this level are engaged in learning, which involves organizing interactions among teachers, students, and content. Hence, it is crucial to guide their exploration process. This implies that learning can be more meaningful in the classroom if the teacher and students work hand in hand.

Table 2. *Level of English Oral Communication Skills of the Students in terms of Speaker’s Knowledge*

Score Range	F	%	Overall Percentage Score	Mean Score	Verbal Interpretation
16-20	2	7.69	68.27	13.65	Developing
10-15	24	92.31			

Legend: “Proficient (16-20)”, “Developing (10-15)”, “Emerging (0-5)”

Table 2 presents the level of English oral communication skills of the students in terms of speaker knowledge before the implementation of Project-Based Learning.

The table shows that the students’ English oral communication skills are at the “*developing*” level regarding their knowledge of speaking. This mean that the students are in attempt to adapt the effective engagement during the speaking process. The students’ scores range from 10 to 15, with a frequency of 24 (92.31%), a mean score of 13.65, and an overall percentage score of 68.27.

This implies that the students are not well-equipped to speak in public, as their knowledge of public speaking is still developing. Tas (2022) posited that to achieve effective, efficient, and appealing learning outcomes; students must have a solid understanding of the subject matter, which includes organizing and presenting information in line with instructional objectives and student characteristics. This may mean that teaching-learning process in the classroom implies solid understanding on the subject matter, instructional objectives, and student’s characteristics. Hence, teacher should establish the solid ground for teaching speaking in the classroom.

Table 3. *Level of English Oral Communication Skills of the Students in terms of Audience Adaptation*

Score Range	F	%	Overall Percentage Score	Mean Score	Verbal Interpretation
16-20	1	3.85	69.04	13.81	Developing
10-15	25	96.15			

Legend: "Proficient (16-20)", "Developing (10-15)", "Emerging (0-5)"

Table 3 reveals the level of english oral communication skills of the students in terms of audience adaptation before the implementation of Project-Based Learning.

This further indicates that the students' scores range from 10 to 15, with a frequency of 25 (96.15%), a mean score of 13.81, and an overall percentage score of 69.04, which signifies a "developing" level which mean the students can partially engage the audience. This suggests that the students cannot consistently engage the audience effectively. Oradee (2018) explains that to engage the audience, speakers should be exposed to authentic environments that allow them to use English for communication and expression. This may imply that authentic environments contribute to the learning of the students.

Table 4. *Level of English Oral Communication Skills of the Students in terms of Language Use*

Score Range	F	%	Overall Percentage Score	Mean Score	Verbal Interpretation
10-15	25	96.15	66.67	13.35	Developing
0-5	1	3.85			

Legend: "Proficient (16-20)", "Developing (10-15)", "Emerging (0-5)"

Table 4 shows the students' english oral communication skills regarding language use before implementing Project-Based Learning.

Based on the investigation, the student's English oral communication skills are still at the "developing" level, which means that they can use language appropriately yet inconsistently, and their word choice is not vivid and precise. Their scores ranged from 10 to 15, with a frequency of 25 (96.15%) and a mean score of 13.35, resulting in an overall percentage score of 66.67.

This implies that while the language may be appropriate, the word choices are not particularly vivid or precise. According to Agustine (2021), language plays a vital role in human life. People use language to express their thoughts and emotions, satisfy their needs or desires, communicate with others, and establish and maintain social

relationships. Hence, the choice of language must be appropriate to facilitate meaningful conversations.

Table 5. *Level of English Oral Communication Skills of the Students in terms of Delivery (Non-Verbal)*

Score Range	F	%	Overall Percentage Score	Mean Score	Verbal Interpretation
16-20	1	3.85	70	14	Developing
10-15	25	96.15			

Legend: "Proficient (16-20)", "Developing (10-15)", "Emerging (0-5)"

Table 5 presents the students' english oral communication skills in terms of delivery (nonverbal) before the implementation of Project-Based Learning.

Based on the table, the students' delivery is at the "developing" stage which mean that the delivery is generally effective however some components are missing. Most students garnered scores within the range of 10 to 15, with a frequency of 25 (96.15%) and a mean score of 14, resulting in an overall percentage score of 70.

This indicates that while the delivery may be effective, the consistent use of volume, eye contact, vocal control, and other elements is lacking. The students appear hesitant, which may be evident in their vocal tone, facial expressions, clothing, and other nonverbal cues. According to Munz and Remland (2021), speech delivery pedagogy has mainly been stagnant, while our understanding of nonverbal behaviors has grown exponentially. Hence, in learning the art of speaking, teachers should consider nonverbal cues during instruction.

Part II. Level of English Oral Communication Skills of the Students after using the Project-Based Learning Approach

Table 6. *Level of English Oral Communication Skills of the Students in terms of organization*

Score Range	F	%	Overall Percentage Score	Mean Score	Verbal Interpretation
16-20	14	53.85	79.23	15.85	Proficient
10-15	12	46.15			

Legend: "Proficient (16-20)", "Developing (10-15)", "Emerging (0-5)"

Table 6 reveals the level of organizational in English oral communication skills after the implementation of Project-Based Learning.

After implementing the STEP program, students achieve a “*proficient*” level in organization skills this mean that the students demonstrate clear and well-organized speech presentation after the PBL program. Most students scored within the range of 16 to 20, with a frequency of 14 (53.85%) and a mean score of 15.85, resulting in an overall percentage of 79.83.

This indicates that students’ organizational skills in public speaking improve after the intervention and further practice. Public speaking skills tend to improve with more practice. Therefore, speaking skills can be trained and developed to enhance students’ communication abilities (Sulistyawati & Yulianti, 2021). Thus, organization in public speaking can be improved through proper intervention and practice. Moreover, students can further organize, develop, and support their ideas to achieve a clear purpose in their speaking; this can be realized as soon as the teacher utilizes the program during instruction.

Table 7. *Level of English Oral Communication Skills of the Students in terms of Speaker’s Knowledge*

Score Range	F	%	Overall Percentage Score	Mean Score	Verbal Interpretation
16-20	16	61.54	77.31	15.46	Proficient
10-15	10	38.46			

Legend: “Proficient (16-20)”, “Developing (10-15)”, “Emerging (0-5)”

Table 7 shows the level of English oral communication skills of the students in terms of speaker knowledge after the implementation of Project-Based Learning.

The students’ score range is 16 to 20, with a frequency of 16 (61.54%), a mean score of 15.46, and an overall percentage score of 77.31, indicating a “*proficient*” level which mean that the student’s knowledge is enhance and they develop clear understanding and knowledge in speaking.

This suggests that the student’s level regarding “*speaker knowledge*” becomes proficient wherein they can grasp the information, appropriately and accurately introduce the citations and include original, logical, and relevant supporting material. This means that they can demonstrate full knowledge of the topic at hand. Thus, through the PBL strategy, students enhance their knowledge in public speaking. Sulistyawati and Yulianti (2021) state that “very frequently, learning is thought of in terms only of adding more knowledge, whereas students should also consider how to bring about change or

transformation of their preexisting knowledge.” This implies that the enhancement program can be a tool for developing the student’s knowledge and transforming them into an effective speaker. This can happen during classroom instruction.

Table 8. *Level of English Oral Communication Skills of the Students in terms of Audience adaptation*

Score Range	F	%	Overall Percentage Score	Mean Score	Verbal Interpretation
16-20	19	73.08	79.42	15.88	Proficient
10-15	7	26.92			

Legend: “Proficient (16-20)”, “Developing (10-15)”, “Emerging (0-5)”

Table 8 shows the students’ english oral communication skills regarding audience adaptation after implementing Project-Based Learning.

Based on the investigation, the student’s level of audience adaptation was enhanced after the program’s implementation which mean that the students can engage the audience and can deliver effective speech. Their score, which ranged from 10 to 15 before the implementation, improved to 16 to 20, with a frequency of 19 (73.08%) and a mean score of 15.88, resulting in an overall percentage score of 79.42.

This indicates that the students can effectively keep the audience engaged. They utilize their non-verbal behaviors to capture the audience’s attention and modify their delivery style to suit the target audience. Additionally, the students choose exciting and relevant topics for their audience and the occasion. Even though varying notions of audiences come with different discursive “baggage,” most imply a common interest in audiences as behavioristic beings (Peters et al., 2020). Hence, audience adaptation is significantly improved which implies that this enhancement strategy can be utilized in teaching-learning process.

Table 9. *Level of English Oral Communication Skills of the Students in terms of Language Use*

Score Range	F	%	Overall Percentage Score	Mean Score	Verbal Interpretation
16-20	13	50.00	77.88	15.58	Developing
10-15	13	50.00			

Legend: “Proficient (16-20)”, “Developing (10-15)”, “Emerging (0-5)”

Table 9 shows the students' English oral communication skills regarding Language use after implementing Project-based learning.

This implies that the “*language use*” is between “developing” and “Proficient.” This means that the student’s language is appropriate, but at times, their word choices are not mostly vivid or precise. However, they are starting to learn to use the language more precisely and accurately.

Furthermore, this suggests that the students’ language choices are becoming more vivid and precise. They can explore the language freely and without bias, using “code-switch” when needed and appropriate to the context. According to William et al., (2021), the use of personal language should center first and foremost on the needs and autonomy of the speaker to ensure clear communication. Hence, during instruction, this implies that the enhancement program can be utilized to create independent speakers among the students.

Table 10. *Level of English Oral Communication Skills of the Students in terms of delivery (Non-Verbal)*

Score Range	F	%	Overall Percentage Score	Mean Score	Verbal Interpretation
16-20	18	69.23	80	16	Proficient
10-15	8	30.77			

Legend: “Proficient (16-20)”, “Developing (10-15)”, “Emerging (0-5)”

Table 10 reveals the students' english oral communication skills in terms of delivery (nonverbal) after the implementation of Project-Based Learning.

Based on the investigation, the students' delivery level is categorized as “*proficient*,” which means that the students clearly articulate and pronounce the words after the intervention. Hence, the audience members can comprehend their presentation without difficulty.

. This suggests that the students can naturally and confidently speak in public. They effectively utilize appropriate posture, eye contact, smooth gestures, and facial expressions and can modulate the tone, volume, and pace of their voice. These indicate that they consistently employ appropriate nonverbal cues, enhancing their communication skills

Part 3: Mean Gain in the English Oral Communication Skills of the Students before and after using the Project-Based Learning Approach

Table 11. Mean Gain in the English Oral Communication Skills of the Students before and after using the Project-Based Learning Approach

Components	Pre-Test Mean	Post-Test Mean	Mean Gain	
Organization	13.38	15.85	2.47	▲
Topic Knowledge	13.65	15.46	1.81	▲
Audience Adaptation	13.81	15.88	2.07	▲
Language Use (Verbal Effectiveness)	13.35	15.58	2.23	▲
Delivery (Non-Verbal Effectiveness)	14.00	16.00	2.00	▲

Table 11 presents the pre-test and post-test mean scores across the five (5) components presented in the rubric.

The pre-test mean reflects the students' initial performance, and the post-test mean reflects their performance after the intervention. The mean gain results of each component, showing improvement across all areas.

The highest mean gain was in '*organization*', with a score of 2.4 points from 13.38 to 15.85, indicating an improvement on how students structured their output, which suggests that the intervention helped the students to enhance their ability in organizing their ideas effectively.

It was followed by the '*language Use*' at a mean gain of 2.23 points from 13.35 to 15.58 reflects a considerable improvement in verbal communication. This indicates that the students became more effective in the use of language possibly through better articulation and clarity in expressing their ideas.

A mean gain of 2.07 points from 13.81 to 15.99 shows the improvement in the students' ability to adapt their message for the "*audience*". This suggests that the students became more adept at considering their audience's needs and adjusting their communication accordingly.

When it comes to the mean gain of "*delivery*" it has 2.00 points (14.00 to 16.000) which indicates that a notable improvement in the non-verbal aspects of communication. This suggests that the students were able to enhance their Oral Communication skills.

However, while all the areas improved, the "*topic knowledge*" showed a slightly smaller gain compared to others. implementing the intervention, all components positively affected the students' oral communication skills.

In general, there is an overall positive trend in the data, with all components showing improvements.

Part 4: Test of Significant effect of the Project-Based Learning approach on the English Oral Communication Skills of the Students

Table 12. *Significant difference of the Project-based Learning Approach on the English Oral Communication Skills of the Students*

Independent Samples Test

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Organization	Equal variances assumed	4.338	.042	-2.215	50	.031	-.30769	.13889	-.58666	-.02873
	Equal variances are not assumed.			-2.215	49.932	.031	-.30769	.13889	-.58667	-.02872
Speaker Knowledge	Equal variances assumed	43.267	.000	-4.854	50	.000	-.53846	.11094	-.76129	-.31563
	Equal variances are not assumed.			-4.854	38.761	.000	-.53846	.11094	-.76290	-.31402
Audience Adaptation	Equal variances assumed	34.764	.000	-7.160	50	.000	-.69231	.09669	-.88652	-.49810
	Equal variances are not assumed.			-7.160	34.078	.000	-.69231	.09669	-.88879	-.49582
Language Use	Equal variances assumed	115.023	.000	-5.804	50	.000	-.61538	.10603	-.82835	-.40241

	Equal variances are not assumed.			-5.804	32.406	.000	-.61538	.10603	-.83126	-.39951
Delivery	Equal variances assumed	49.170	.000	-6.538	50	.000	-.65385	.10000	-.85470	-.45299
	Equal variances are not assumed.			-6.538	33.427	.000	-.65385	.10000	-.85720	-.45049

Note: “If the *p*-value is less than or equal to the significance level (0.05), reject *H*₀; otherwise, fail to reject *H*₀.”

Table 12 presents Levene’s test for the equality of variances, showing the significant difference of the Project-based Learning approach on the students’ Oral Communication Skills before and after the program’s implementation.

Based on the investigation, the *organization* with a significance level of 0.042, *speaker knowledge*, *audience adaptation*, *language use*, and *delivery (non-verbal)* are all with a level of significance of 0.000, which is less than the significance level (0.05). Therefore, the STEP Program, Project-Based Learning, significantly affects the level of students’ Oral Communication skills at Magsaysay National High School. Hence, the hypothesis on the significance of the PBL program is rejected. This implies that the students improve their oral communication skills after the STEP program intervention.

This further explains that students’ oral communication skills can be improved through consistent drills, practice, an appropriate program, and close guidance from the teacher.

Part 5: Produced Project-Based Learning Enhancement Strategy

In this section, the researcher presents the Project-Based Learning Enhancement Strategy as an output of this investigation.

The PBLP on the English Oral Communication Skills of the Students emphasizes active participation, where students take ownership of their learning. Working on projects that require speaking, discussion, and collaboration which make them fosters active engagement and also it promotes deeper understanding and retention of language skills.

In addition, The STEP Program utilizing the Project-based Learning approach is a program that can be used to enhance the learner’s English oral communication skills.

DISCUSSION

From the analysis and interpretations of the data collected, the following findings are presented:

1. Before implementing the Project-based Learning Approach, the Student's English oral communication skills were at a "*developing*" level. Their scores ranged from 10 to 15. The students' organization level was 73.08%, with a frequency of 19 and a mean score of 13.38. Their 'speaker knowledge' was 92.31%, with a frequency of 24, a mean score of 13.65, and an overall percentage of 68.27. Additionally, 'audience adaptation,' 'language use,' and delivery (non-verbal) all scored 96.15%, with a frequency of 25 and a mean score of 14.
2. After implementing the Project-based Learning approach, the student's level of English oral communication was assessed as "proficient." The scores ranged from 16 to 20, with the following results: 'Organization' with frequency of 14 (53.85%), mean score of 15.85, and overall percentage of 79.23. 'Speaker knowledge' with a frequency of 16 (61.58%), mean score of 15.46, and overall percentage of 77.31. 'Audience adaptation' with a frequency of 19 (73.08%), mean score of 15.88, and overall percentage of 79.42. 'Language use' has an equal frequency (13) within score ranges of 10-15 and 16-20, equivalent to 50%, with a mean score of 15.58 and an overall score of 77.88. 'Delivery (non-verbal)' has a frequency of 13 (69.23%), a mean score of 16, and an overall percentage of 80.
3. After implementing the PBL, students' scores improved significantly. The highest mean gain was observed in "*organization*," with a score of 2.4, followed closely by "*language use*," which had a mean gain of 2.23. The area showing the most minor improvement was the speaker's topic knowledge, with a mean gain of 1.81.
4. The test of significance on the effect of the Project-Based Learning approach on the English Oral Communication Skills of the students indicated that the null hypothesis should be rejected if the p-value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05) and the Levene's test of equality of variance results on the different criteria that gauge the oral communication skills of the students: 'organization' with a significance level of .042, 'speaker knowledge,' 'audience adaptation,' 'language use' and 'delivery (non-verbal)' were all on the significance level of 0.000, results were less than the p-value and this means that the PBL has significant effect to the enhancement of the student's oral communication skills.
5. The output that was produced out of this investigation is the Project-Based Learning Plan which is a program that can be used to enhance the Student's English Oral Communication Skills.

Conclusions

From the results of the study, the following conclusions are drawn:

1. The students' oral communication skills before the implementation of the Project-Based Learning (PBL) approach, in terms of organization, speaker knowledge, audience adaptation, language use, and delivery (non-verbal), were still in the "developing" stage. This indicates that the students required further guided practice.
2. After implementing the PBL approach, the students' oral communication skills, including organization, speaker knowledge, audience adaptation, language use, and delivery (non-verbal), improved, and they became "proficient." Implementing PBL significantly improved students' mean gains, particularly in oral communication skills.
3. The PBL approach significantly enhanced the students' oral communication skills.
4. The Project-Based Learning Approach has significant effect on the English Oral Communication Skills of the Students. Thus, the research hypothesis is rejected.
5. The Project Based Learning Plan was the output of the investigation.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are offered:

1. Teachers may use the Project-Based Learning (PBL) approach to facilitate classroom learning effectively. Students can benefit from this method by exploring and experiencing learning creatively and functionally.
2. Since the PBL approach effectively enhances students' english oral communication skills, teachers may maximize the use of this program. It can be a valuable tool for improving students' communicative competence and making classroom learning more engaging.
3. Given the significant effect of PBL on students' english oral communication development, school administrators may support teachers in further developing the program. Administrators can create avenues to make the teaching and learning process more innovative and proactive.
4. Future researchers may continue to enhance the STEP program to further improve students' academic performance in oral communication and communicative competence, with additional parameters serving as resources for further study.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study ensured the informed consent was given to the following respondents. Freedom to withdraw from the study at any time, anonymity of the respondents was maintained, the respondents' well-being was safeguarded, no conflict of interests exists in the conduct of the study, plagiarism was strictly avoided, there was no bias in the interpretation of the findings and that the results were used purely for research.

Acknowledgments

The researcher wishes to express her heartfelt gratitude and appreciation to those who have been very instrumental in the realization of this study:

Foremost, our GOD ALMIGHTY, the provider and source of all enlightenment and power, for giving her knowledge, perseverance, hope and determination to make her study possible.

First and foremost, the researcher's utmost gratitude is extended to Marinduque State University Graduate School Extended to Eastern Quezon College, Inc.

To Marinduque State University President Dr. Diosdado P. Zulueta, for his leadership and selfless assistance when needed;

To Dr. Leodegario M. Jalos, Jr., Chairperson of Extended Graduate Programs of Marinduque State University, for his untiring support, technical assistance and continuous guidance to the researcher in order for this study to be a success;

To Dr. Melchor B. Espiritu, Dean of Graduate Studies of Eastern Quezon College, Inc., for her encouragement and moral support for seeing this research through to the end;

To Dr. Susan B. Pineda, her thesis adviser, for all the patience, guidance, encouragement, and knowledge to provide needed suggestions for the improvement of the study and for affording the essential materials for research;

To Ms. Maria Teresa C. Chavez, her statistician; Mr. Jerome L. Lingon, her editor; and Dr. Ernesto L. Largado, her copy editor, for their great help in accomplishing this study;

Acknowledgment is also given to the members of the Oral Examination:

To Dr. Diosdado P. Zulueta, Dr. Melchor B. Espiritu, and Dr. Annalyn J. Decena, for their valuable input, which led to the success of this study;

To Ms. Liezl M. Manoy, for attending to queries of the researcher whenever there is a need to clarify about this study;

To Ms. Lydia F. Salumbides, Ms. Menching L. Samson, and Ms. Joyyeth Marrie T. Bautista for validating and improving the research instrument of this study;

To Ms. Aurea M. Osen, School Head of Magsaysay National High School, for letting the researcher conduct the pilot testing of the instrument;

To Ms. Rebie A. Marciano, Public School District Supervisor of Mulanay District 1 and for allowing the researcher to conduct her study in her respective district;

To Ms. Noime L. Limpiada, her special someone, for the inspiration;

To all of her friends and colleagues especially to Jessica C. Mendoza, Mark L. Pulbos, Editha L. Amisola, Bryan Christian P. Noves for their moral support, prayers, and encouragement to work hard and accomplish this study; and

To Grade 11 learners of Magsaysay National High School, for actively participating in the conduct of study;

To all great and wonderful people whose names do not appear above for whatever assistance extended with sincerity, a million thanks to each one of you.

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